

DRUGS & FINE CHEMICALS

Pfizer, Inc. has followed last week's 25 cent price cut on ascorbic acid by Hoffman-La Roche, Inc. While demand for ascorbic continues as strong, Pfizer's move to reduce ascorbic acid to \$3.85 per kilo was initiated to maintain competitive pricing with Roche. Spokesmen for other producers report their companies continue holding to the \$4.10 price, but assert the firms are "studying the situation." One of these observers reports the firm's primary consideration will be the relation of operating costs to selling price. In our case, says another trade source, the primary consideration is how to balance the desire "to maintain a stable yet reasonable price," and concedes the balance already appears difficult.

Whether or not a split-price market can be maintained for ascorbic acid reportedly depends on whether there is an imbalance of supply and demand, as was the case last year. Last week, producers' comments on the present market situation of ascorbic acid point to a continuing strong demand for ascorbic.

Ascorbic Sales Still Strong

One source formerly reported pharmaceutical demand has slackened in 1972, not unrelated to the fall in consumer interest for Dr. Linus Pauling's Vitamin C studies. In turn, there was speculation in the trade that ascorbic sales activity in 1972 would fall short of expectations.

Last week, however, nearly all producers' sources affirm that ascorbic sales for pharmaceutical applications are notably picking up, and that the overall market, including ascorbic material for food fortification uses, is strong. At present, he adds, "we can't supply enough."

If the Roche plant planned to go on stream later this year meets its schedule, ascorbic acid capacity in the U.S. reportedly would double from its present estimated annual total of about 12 million pounds a year.

In turn, if an imbalance of supply and demand would therein be lifted by the new facility, sources speculate that a two-price market would possibly be difficult to maintain.

While US exports of ascorbic acid for the first six months of 1972 show a 22 percent increase from those exported in the first six months of last year, ascorbic acid entries for this year continue on the down side.

Official statistics show an 11 percent drop in ascorbic acid entries during the January to September period, against the same period in 1971. This year's cumulative total is 4,423,548 pounds; last year's total was 4,994,561 pounds.

Two factors are suggested by a trade source as reasons for the decline—firmer prices in Europe, coupled with an active rate of overseas demand for ascorbic acid both in European and Far East markets.

West German Imports Cited

Another change in ascorbic imports for 1972 is in source of supply. Out of 1971's total, Japan was the leading supplier, accounting for 2.4 million pounds. Data for this year's nine-month period, however, attribute the greatest amount of ascorbic entries to West Germany, with 1,833,985 pounds. Japan follows, with 1,703,180 pounds.

One source explains that some of this West German ascorbic material is actually a leading US ascorbic acid producer's. According to a spokesman for this firm, ascorbic acid, on occasion, is brought in to supplement domestic supplies.

1972 edition of Handbook of Japan Drug Industry notes that ascorbic acid output in Japan increased four times the

THE WEEK'S PRICE CHANGES

Ending November 10, 1972

ADVANCED	
None	
REDUCED	
Silver cyanide, 80% Ag., 1.7c. per oz.	
Silver nitrate, ACS, 3.0c. per oz.	

COMPARATIVE PRICE INDEXES (100=1959 average)			
Last Week	Prev. Week	Last Month	Nov. 12, 1971
80.86	80.85	80.83	80.73

For Current Prices See Page 33

amount recorded at the beginning of the decade. In 1961, an estimated 755 tons were produced; in 1970, the figure soared to 2,998,357 tons. Over half that amount—1,547,500 tons—was allocated for export.

According to data compiled by Stanford Research Institute, Japan supplied 62 percent of US ascorbic imports in 1970. Last week, a trade source for a major Japanese producer estimates that about half of Japan's current exports are earmarked for the US.

The remaining portion of Japanese material is reported to be spread among Asian, African, and European consumers.

Erythorbic Acid—Producers report erythorbic acid continues to move at \$1.59 for 200-pound drum quantities. Also known as isoascorbic acid, the granular crystals serve as antioxidants, and a major customer is reportedly the brewing industry.

Product Sales—Fifty-six member firms of the Pharmaceutical Manufacturers Association have reported product sales by therapeutic class, accounting for about 85 percent of industry's sales of prescription drugs in dosage form for human use.

The recent product breakdown shows that drugs for respiratory diseases have declined markedly in their share of the total market. From 1968 to 1971, this category showed a 14 percent drop in sales volume—from \$288 million to \$249 million.

Dermatological preparations and diagnostic agents have experienced the greatest increase in product sales during the same three year period. Dermatological preparations have gone up 74 percent; diagnostic agents, 87 percent.

Central nervous system products remain the most important sales category of the market, with sales totaling \$973 million. Anti-infectives are second, with sales of more than one-half billion dollars. The PMA survey notes that the two groups have not changed their strong positions since 1965.

Sodium Ascorbate—Hoffman-La Roche, Inc. has announced a 25c. reduction in sodium ascorbate prices, in accordance with its November 6 announcement of a decrease in the price of ascorbic acid.

Effective November 6, Roche is offering the USP grade material at \$4.40 per kilo.

Drug and Fine Chemical Imports: September

Imports of selected drugs and fine chemicals for August and September, as reported by the Bureau of Census, are as follows:

	August		September	
	Volume	\$ Value	Volume	\$ Value
Ascorbic acid, salts	501,995	937,846	536,821	1,029,303
Caffeine	162,979	276,719	167,769	274,206
Camphor, Nat. crude				
nat. adv.			27,558	29,688
syn.	103,488	51,874	40,479	20,003
Cream of tartar	295,476	90,366	132,092	42,176
Iodine, crude	514,000	877,361	690,700	1,118,811
Menthol	178,851	922,179	166,200	742,273
Methionine	1,875,750	995,889	2,475,037	1,346,099
Monosodium glutamate	675,104	222,509	607,395	193,003
Niacin, amide, syn.	231,454	300,188	118,255	178,318
Pyridoxine, syn.	18,033	84,500	8,267	38,010
Quinidine, salts	277,471	666,366	163,523	362,484
Quinine, salts	108,611	192,233	72,601	128,094
Saccharin	128,451	196,508	135,904	222,001
Sodium alginate	5,000	4,215		
Tartaric acid	560,584	215,072	450,725	172,675
Thiamine	8,714	50,194	18,344	102,368
Vitamin A	212,672	469,586	141,545	418,131
Vitamins, nspf	98,714	189,732	182,832	307,638

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ALIPHATIC ORGANICS

Vinyl Acetate Mart's Big Three
Are Turning on New Capacity

Rhone-Progil's Plant Sites in France

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AJINOMOTO
COMPANY OF NEW YORK, INC.

745 Fifth Avenue, New York, N.Y. 10022. Telephone: (212) 688-8360
LOS ANGELES BRANCH:
650 S. Grand Ave., Los Angeles, Calif. 90017. Telephone: (213) 629-2576